

Error detection and comparison of gesture control technologies

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ABSTRACT

This paper showcases the study and observation on the error occurrence in gesture control technologies. An arduino-based gesture control environment has been developed by using the arduino board to use motion gestures to control the contents on the screen. This environment is made using position sensitive diodes as sensing devices, arduino as a micro-controller and Python to execute commands in the system. It is performed on 2 different software applications namely Google Chrome and VideoLAN Client Media Player. In Google Chrome gestures are used to traverse between tabs and also move up and down within a web page, whereas in VideoLAN Client Media Player gestures are used to control the volume and speed. Through this, the difference between two technologies i.e., infrared and ultrasonic are worked and compared. Various data visualization cues are prepared to better understand the error and the factors causing it. Thorough investigation of factors affecting the error has been done using our observation. The future of this technology and its limitations have been also discussed.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper illustrates error occurrences and drawbacks of using ultrasonic technology for gesture control through the project Gesture control for computers using ultrasonic sensors [1]. Earlier interaction between computer and human was only limited to keyboard and mouse, but today you can interact with gestures i.e facial recognition, and hand gestures [2]. Gestures and image recognition are used in human skin detection [3]. Gestures being the primitive form of communication within humans, these are highly useful for computer interaction [4], [5]. Dynamic gesture recognition of human gestures makes up an important means of user-machine interface [6]. Gesture controls are used in computer vision for human computer interaction with electromyography [7]–[9]. Automated recognition of human gesture is a boon for user interfacing [10]. Human hand gestures have become more natural and with the help of wireless communication [11], various gestures of the computer can be controlled using these sensors and hand recognition [12]. Gestures are detected using optical and motion technology by the means of bluetooth, acoustics, tactiles, or infrared waves [13]. In the vision based system, motion and skin color information is utilized to detect waving hands requesting control commands [14]. Research is still very active in unresolved challenges such as reliable input such as identification of gestures, sensitivity to variations in size, shape, speed and issues due to occlusion [15]. Making a cost efficient highly accurate model for a gesture control system is essential for the future [16].

Vision-based gesture recognition models are based on gesture detection and classification, feature extraction and pre-programmed template execution process [17]. Various gestures of the computer can be controlled using these sensors and hand recognition. Hand recognition based on visual technology is an active area of research from ages [18]–[20]. These approaches are based on distance and accuracy which are quite flexible, but sometimes they make wrong detection on lighting changes and reflection. There are not many practical hand gesture recognition systems that use visual technologies due to its inaccuracy despite its cost efficiency [21]. One of the prime features of using hand gestures is to interact with the computer as an input unit [22], [23]. So, this paper presents the study on the most cost-efficient models and ways to increase their accuracy. These models are precisely demonstrated using two techniques namely infrared and ultrasonic sensors.

In the present work, each model was provided with six numbers of gestures to manipulate the screen motions and gestures were set and programmed accordingly in the Arduino integrated development environment and using python programming language, commands were given to the display [24]. Distance between sensor and hand are measured using sensors, which helps to detect the type of movement and then the computer shows the result [25]–[27]. Then accuracy of gestures was quantified and represented in pie charts using proper data visualization techniques in Jupyter notebook. Differences in accuracy between two technologies were quantified and results were concluded. Figure 1 shows the flow of function in an ideal gesture control system. Input is given to the system which is then read by the sensing devices. Then the microcontroller interprets and processes the information. After interpretation a command or a signal is given to the system. This command or signal interacts with the output or display such that favorable changes are made in the display or output. Figure 2 shows the flow of function in a proximity based ideal gesture control system. Gesture is given as input to the system which is then read by the proximity sensors. Then the microcontroller interprets and processes the information. After interpretation a command or a signal is given to the system. This command or signal interacts with the output or display such that favorable changes are made in the output.

Figure 1. Flow chart for an ideal gesture control device

Figure 2. Flow chart for proximity sensor-based gesture control system

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Gesture control system using ultrasonic sensor

Different components are required to develop the gesture control system using ultrasonic sensors. Those are Arduino UNOx1, ultrasonic sensorsx2, USB cable (for Arduino), a device for programming and display (PC) and jump wires. Figures 3 and 4 depicts the circuit diagram for ultrasonic sensor-based gesture control systems.

The trigger and echo pins of the first ultrasonic sensor are connected with pins 8 and 9 of the Arduino while pins 2 and 3 of the Arduino are connected with the trigger and echo pins of the second ultrasonic sensor. The two ultrasonic sensors are placed on two corners of the display, i.e., the left and right side of the PC display in our case. If they are placed too close then the signal will interfere and wrong results will come. After checking the connections, serial inputs are set in the Arduino IDE representing each input point in the circuit. In the loop function separate functions for the left, right, up and down gestures are defined. The distance is calculated using the principle of reflection of sound. When a sound wave travels back to us after reflecting a surface, the distance is given by,

$$Distance = Speed \times (time/2) \quad (1)$$

Half the total time is taken because sound covers the same distance to travel twice. Now, the speed of sound at sea level is 343 m/s.

$$Distance = (343/2) \times time \quad (in\ m) \quad (2)$$

Therefore,

$$Distance = (17150) \times time \quad (in\ cm) \quad (3)$$

In the next step a particular range is defined at which the hand can move towards and away from the sensor. Those distances are taken to be 10 to 30 cm to avoid any other noise or disturbance that could occur in the background while using this technology. Now since the boundary at which our system works is decided, now the system is set to form our command for the right- and left-hand movements. Commands are set in such a way that sensors identify the movement of hands from one sensor to another by using reflected sound waves on both the sensors in a given time interval.

Figure 3. Circuit diagram for ultrasonic sensor-based gesture control system

Figure 4. Circuit for ultrasonic sensor-based gesture control systems

2.2. Gesture control system using infrared sensor

Components required to develop the gesture control system using infrared sensors [28] are: Arduino UNOx1, 2xIR sensor, USB cable (for Arduino), a device for programming and display (PC) and jump wires. Figures 5 and 6 depict the circuit diagram for an IR based gesture control system. passive infrared sensors are used for enhancing sensing reliability [29].

Associated a jumper wire in the collector pin of the integrated circuit to utilize this sensor as a simple sensor. To perceive signal developments utilizing IR sensors, a trigger system is utilized. Let two IR sensors be placed on opposite sides of the display and named left-IR and right-IR. Additionally, place your IR sensor such that there is around 3 cm of hole between them. Code has been set up on the arduino according to the principle of reflection of light. 2 sets of infrared sensors each having a receiver and a producing part are prepared. The pins are carefully connected to the arduino circuit board, later these pins are set to arduino IDE. Now functions for different gesture motions are declared. The gesture 1 and gesture 2 are programmed in such a way that the sensor recognizes how far can our arms from and away from itself, the data from the serial monitor is obtained and likewise it is fed to the python program. Meanwhile the programs of gesture 5, gesture 6 and gesture 4 are actuated in such a way that both the sensor checks the vicinity of the object to one another, likewise, these sensors now capture the wave movement of the hand.

2.3. Programming Arduino to detect gestures

Different cases are made to distinguish gestures from each other based on the distance measured by the sensors over a time period which is unique to a particular gesture. Creating different cases for different gestures makes it possible to execute different commands on sensing different gestures which is done by the help of python. Following are the cases:

- Gesture 1: Place your palm in front of the right sensor and move towards yourself (distance of palm from sensors should be between 15 to 35 cm). This motion will scroll down your page in the browser or decrease the volume in the media player.

- Gesture 2: Place your palm in front of the right sensor and move towards sensors (distance of palm from sensors should be between 15 to 35 cm). This motion will scroll up your page in the browser or increase the volume in the media player.
- Gesture 3: Swipe your hand in front of the right ultrasonic sensor. This motion will change your current tab to the Next Tab or fast forward the video running in the media player by 10 seconds.
- Gesture 4: Swipe your hand in front of the left ultrasonic sensor. This motion will change your current Tab to the previous tab or backward the video running in the media player by 10 seconds.
- Gesture 5: Swipe your both palms in front of both sensors simultaneously (left palm a little bit fast).

Figure 5. Circuit diagram for IR sensor based gesture control system

Figure 6. Circuit for IR sensor based gesture control system

This motion switches between tasks (i.e., browser and media player). The automation code for the software actuation is programmed in python, different codes are used for different software which are internet browser and video player respectively. In python code PyAutoGUI is used to read the commands of the arduino IDE provided to the Python code [30].

- if 'next' is given as input the system produces pagedown activity.
- if 'previous' is given as input the system produces pageup activity.
- if 'down' is given as input the system produces scroll down activity.
- if 'up' is given as input the system produces scroll up activity.
- if 'change' is given as input the system produces change tab activity in the browser.

Control gestures used for the video player are the same as browsers but have different executions. The same PyAutoGUI is used for controlling the output from arduino IDE as well as managing the hotkey functions in the keyboard. The gestures are given below:

- if 'next' is given as input the system produces a move forward signal for 10 seconds activity.
- if 'previous' is given as input the system produces a move backwards signal for 10 seconds activity.
- if 'down' is given as input the system produces a decrease in volume activity.
- if 'up' is given as input the system produces an increase in volume activity.
- if 'change' is given as input the system produces a pause activity in the video player.

Figure 6 depicts the arduino IDE serial monitor. In Figure 7, this window acts as an interface between the device and the software to exchange information and the message flow to one another through a USB pin. The meaning of the statements in the interface are:

- b'1\r\n' indicates true value or positive value
- b'0\r\n' indicates false value or negative value

Figure 8. Right swipe observations (Ultrasonic)

Figure 9. Left swipe observations (Ultrasonic)

Figure 10. Scroll down observations (Ultrasonic)

Figure 11. Scroll up observations (Ultrasonic)

Figure 12. Right swipe observations using barrier (Ultrasonic)

Figure 13. Left swipe observations (Infrared)

Figure 14. Right swipe observations (Infrared)

Figure 15. Scroll up observations (Infrared)

Figure 16. Scroll down observations (Infrared)

4. CONCLUSION

It has been quantified that IR sensors have a better accuracy in Gesture control technology than ultrasonic sensors. The increase in accuracy has been found out to about 27.874% through our experiment. Among the two technologies, complimenting the gesture motions, studied and compared thoroughly, error observations were noted, which were consolidated into the following conclusions: Cons in using ultrasonic sensors: Its range is up to 400 cm. If multiple sensors are put closely, there will be interference and it will give unwanted output which is unreliable. Moreover, if there is sound absorbing or reflecting material worn by the user or are in very close proximity of the sensors the readings will be faulty resulting in wrong commands given to the system. Cons in using IR sensors: It gives inaccurate reading if encountered with a reflective surface. If the user wears something that is reflective in nature or absorbs the beam of IR, the reading of the IR sensor can become inaccurate. If multiple sensors are put closely, there will be interference and it will give unreliable output. It can maintain high accuracy for a range of 150 cm after that irregularities increase in the readings from the sensor. Ultrasonic sensors work using the principle of sound waves. Their results can be affected due to many factors such as noise, other obstacle interactions, sensor liabilities. But can be used where there is less sound medium based noise and more heat related noise. Infrared, on the other hand, is a more accurate technology considering the gesture technologies and its application. It still has shortcomings; for instance, if there are many heat sources in the environment. Error arising in an ultrasonic sensor due to noise and other matters can be decreased by adding a barrier in between the ultrasonic sensor to decrease the interruption by the sound noises normal to the barrier and isolate the direction to be sensed.

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